

D3.2

In-situ tools, sample designs and protocols

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Abstract	A new in-situ set-up for thermal cycling of copper on silicon (polyheater) samples has been established at IKTS. An exemplary sample was imaged using X-ray transmission imaging, validating the set-up functionality. New sample layouts for 3D imaging were designed and produced at Infineon Technologies Austria and KAI, but could not yet be imaged due to production delays.
Keywords	X-ray imaging, nanoXCT, polyheater, cycling, degradation, in-situ

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Executive Summary

Polyheaters (test chips performing electrical resistance heating) are used to study the thermo-mechanical degradation of thin copper metallization layers in conditions similar to short circuit events in power semiconductor devices. The test chips are cycled using short pulses ($\approx 200\mu\text{s}$) and high heating rates (10^6 K/s). This leads to the formation of voids and cracks in the copper. However, the exact interplay of degradation factors remains elusive and this necessitates high resolution, in-situ, 3D imaging of the degradation processes. Therefore, a new in-situ cycling set-up was deployed and tested at Fraunhofer IKTS, where X-ray microscopes provide the necessary imaging capabilities for high-resolution tomographies.

The new set-up consists of several source measure units, adapters, and an oscilloscope, as well as further contact adapters to the sample (needlecard or wirebonds with special plugs). It achieves similar heating rates and loads to the one employed at KAI, which functions as the control standard for the functionality of the new set-up. However, the exact heating pulse shapes differ, thereby leading to a slight divergence in heating profiles between the two set-ups.

This difference in temperature curve does not impair the general functionality and cycling capabilities of the new IKTS set-up, which is demonstrated by intermittently cycling a sample and then imaging it using the X-ray microscope. It allowed for the tracking of single cracks and their evolution over discrete cycling steps, delivering a proof of concept in two dimensions.

Furthermore, specific sample layouts were designed at KAI to enable non-destructive tomographic in-situ imaging. These samples were designed in such a way, that the bulk of the heating pad does not obscure the incoming X-ray beam, while still retaining heating functionality.

While the general set-up capabilities have been studied and proven, further work remains in the upcoming months, like cycling and 3D imaging of the new sample layouts, as well as imaging the samples with higher X-ray energies.

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Chapter 1 Introduction

During operation of power semiconductor devices, short-circuit events and power overload pulses may lead to significant heat dissipation and an associated increase of the temperature of junction elements. The thermal energy is emitted over a relatively short amount of time (50 μ s) and temperature peaks in the surrounding dielectrics and the metallization can reach amplitudes as high as 400 °C. This may lead to critical failure due to thermal runaway, typically only mitigated by carefully engineered heat sinks close to the junction [1]. Copper metallizations placed on top of silicon devices can act as such heat sinks. However, they also show thermomechanical fatigue upon thermal cycling, due to the mismatch of thermal expansion coefficient between copper and silicon [2]. Creep mechanisms and other stress relaxation processes come into play at such high temperatures, resulting in the formation of cracks and voids. The exact combination and interplay of these various degradation factors remains elusive, as the structural characterization of such complex devices is experimentally difficult, especially under *in-situ* conditions.

We aim to address this challenge by structural characterization of polyheaters. Polyheaters are a class of test chips employing a polycrystalline silicon layer for electrical resistance heating, that can be used for the heating of several kinds of integrated structure [3] in order to mimic short circuit events. Utilizing dedicated polyheaters, the thermal degradation of copper metallizations can be stimulated in a controlled way by cyclically applying precise electric loads (power pulses) and corresponding Joule heating of the material. For this specific purpose, a novel set-up for in situ cycling and monitoring of the copper polyheater metallization was designed at KAI [4].

Polyheater samples examined previously within the frame of this project were pre-cycled at KAI and then imaged at IKTS. This allowed us to become familiar with the imaging protocols, detailed in Deliverable 3.1., and gain a general understanding of the statistical degradation effects within the metallization after certain amounts of cycles. Moreover, we determined the general starting point for the formation of voids and cracks in the material. However, one of the major aims of this project is to improve our understanding in the degradation of copper metallizations. This necessitates a continuous tracking of the evolution of degradation features, like the formation of an individual void and its subsequent evolution into a crack. Therefore, it was imperative that an in-situ cycling set-up, comparable to the one at KAI, is established at IKTS, alongside suitable samples that could be 3D imaged without cutting parts out, therefore retaining functionality and the ability to be cycled further.

1.1 Samples

1.1.1 Introduction to polyheaters

Polyheater test chips are simplified microelectronic devices, to study the thermo-mechanical fatigue of Cu on Si structures (Figure 1a). The specific design enables fast cyclic heating of a Cu structure, indicated as the region of interest (ROI) using electric power pulsing. When applying voltage to the power pads (A), the electrical power is dissipated in a high resistive polysilicon layer, which heats the chip centre (B) including the ROI. The temperature can be determined by resistance measurements via the sensing pads (C). The schematic chip cross-section in Figure 1b shows the sequence of the most relevant layers such as, Si substrate, poly-Si heating layer, SiO₂ dielectric interlayer, Al temperature sensor and the Cu power metallization. Figure 1c displays a representative heating pulse, as applied during thermo-mechanical fatigue tests. Major pulse parameters such as base temperature (T_{Base}), maximum temperature (T_{max}), pulse length, and waiting time between two pulses are independent of each other and can be individually adjusted [4]. To calculate the temperature reached during cycling, it is necessary to measure the room temperature resistance ($R(T_{\text{ref}})$, $T_{\text{ref}} = 20^\circ\text{C}$) of the sample's temperature sensor, as well as track the

evolution of the resistance during a power pulse. The exact formula is shown below in equation 1, with more information found in [5]. The value of $\alpha(T_{ref})$ for all further calculations is $0,00372 \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Equation 1:

$$R(T) = R(T_{ref}) \cdot [1 + \alpha(T_{ref}) \cdot (T - T_{ref})]$$

Figure 1: a) Polyheater chip used for fatigue experiments and nano-XCT. b) Polyheater cross-section showing the stack at the ROI. c) A representative heating and power pulse, which is cyclically applied during thermo-mechanical fatigue test.

1.1.2 2D samples

So far, two key sample design factors have been identified that are necessary for successful imaging of polyheaters at IKTS.

Firstly, the silicon substrate must be thin, ideally not more than $60 \mu\text{m}$ (with additional preparation), or otherwise $120 \mu\text{m}$ (as-fabricated). Secondly, the copper thickness should be optimized for the Xradia X-ray microscope (see Chapter 1.2.1), $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$. Thicker copper structures ($20 \mu\text{m}$) might be usable in the ARMI in the upcoming months. On a sample with these parameters, so called mosaics can be performed, scanning over a given area of interest that can include the complete polyheater area or only the region of interest (ROI) (central lines, thermo-mechanically tested). They are stitched together from several individual transmission images and therefore only provide two-dimensional (2D) information. This method routinely achieves a resolution of about 100nm without the need for synchrotron radiation, enabling the imaging of small void and crack structures, generated by the thermal-mechanical stress from power cycling. The protocols and results by 2D TXM were already showcased in Deliverable D3.1.

Since the 2D samples are not limited by size nor must they account for rotation axes, standard samples retain their functionality (no power pad removal is required) and can therefore easily be cycled and then transferred between the in-situ set-up and the microscope. An exemplary sample is shown in the previous subchapter in Figure 1a. Cycling the sample directly inside the X-ray microscope, without moving the sample, is not possible so far due to the very limited space inside the microscope.

1.1.3 3D samples

In addition to the thickness parameters set for 2D mosaics, samples used for tomographies need to fulfil even more requirements for successful 3D imaging: A thin area of interest (ROI limitations: $40 \mu\text{m}$ line width independent of height) as well as no further copper structures (such as contacting pads) that come into the path of light when rotating the sample. This geometric requirement makes use of the standard polyheater chip without further preparation aside from cycling difficult: During rotation, the amount of sample within the beam increases rapidly, rendering about half the projections of a 180° rotation useless because the sample absorbed too much incoming light and no discernible image of the sample could be captured. This is illustrated in Figure 2a), showing a Polyheater sample cut down in width but still retaining an intact heating area. However, the copper line does not protrude out from the base of the chip compared to the surrounding area, therefore, it is covered up by the remaining material in many projections. The reconstruction of this tomography and segmentation of the cracks within seems accurate only when viewed from the front (Figure 2b), where enough projections could be captured. However, the side view (Figure 2c)

is completely undefined in width and thereby no sharp features can be identified due to the missing angles.

Figure 2: Polyheater sample (50k cycles) slightly cut at the sides, so that only the heating area remains. a) Light microscopy image of cut polyheater, heating area in white, imaged region of interest in red. b) Reconstruction of the void volume in the ROI, front view. c) Reconstruction of the void volume in the ROI, sideview.

Furthermore, there can be no additional copper structures on the sample at the same height position as the chosen area of interest, because during rotation they will pass through the beam and create phantom objects and interferences with the real area of interest. Such phantom objects are visible in Figure 3, where a cut off polyheater sample was imaged. First in Figure 3a), the overview mosaic shows the general sample layout, the ROI (red) as well as underlying via structures (highlighted in green). Both sides of the copper structure only show five via squares, however the reconstructed volume (Figure 3b) shows ten total via squares, an overlay of both sides of the copper line. Thereby, the data is inaccurate in regards to the actual position and occurrence of cracks in the ROI.

Figure 3: Tomography of cut-off polyheater sample. a) Raw overview mosaic image, ROI in red, underlying via structures highlighted in green. b) Reconstructed tomography of the crack network in the ROI, green area shows how the via structure rectangles have doubled compared to the raw mosaic image.

These issues were addressed previously by cutting out large parts of the sample, including the power pads and the central copper structures, an example for this is shown in Figure 4. Only a very small pillar of material with the desired proportions remained in the area of interest. However, the removal of chip-parts integral to the electrical performance such as the power pads impairs the functionality of the polyheater. Therefore, the samples had to be pre-cycled before they were cut. A new design was developed (see Chapter 3) to fabricate samples that can be successfully 3D imaged and remain functional.

Figure 4: Polyheater sample cut down significantly, so that only a single copper line stands isolated. This sample lost all electrical functionality due to the extreme cuts.

1.2 Methodology

1.2.1 X-ray microscopy

Lab-based transmission X-ray microscopy (TXM) is an imaging technique employing X-rays to capture projections of an illuminated sample or sample region. The specific kind of TXM deployed at IKTS is usually called nanoXCT, due to the nanoscale resolution achieved by the use of a Fresnel Zone Plate (FZP) as a magnifying objective (between 100nm and 50nm depending on the chosen field of view and size of the imaged object) and the usage of computed tomographies (CTs) to enable three-dimensional (3D) tomographic imaging [6] [7]. The IKTS X-ray laboratory contains several X-ray sources, which are operating at different photon energies depending on the anode material, in particular the Cu K-alpha source at 8.04 keV of the Xradia X-ray microscope and a different X-ray microscope operating with a dual energy In-Ga source at 9 keV and 24 keV. Currently, we were unable to obtain in-situ TXM images with Gallium or Indium energy due to continuous technical problems with the X-ray microscopy using the dual-energy source (so called ARMI). A first few attempts at imaging the cycled samples were taken, however, the cycled samples proved to be too transparent to the high energy X-rays, therefore no sample features could be identified. Currently, samples with thicker copper (20 μm) are being investigated, though the results were not ready for this Deliverable. Further information regarding the general imaging setup of the microscopes and protocols for 2D (mosaics) and 3D (tomographies) imaging were reported in deliverable D3.1.

Chapter 2 The in-situ thermal cycling set-up at IKTS

2.1 Hardware solution

With the limited photon flux achieved at laboratory X-ray sources, it is not possible to image the effect and happenings during one unique cycle (timespan $200\ \mu\text{s}$) with a microscope that needs several minutes to take a single high-resolution projection. Thus, it was decided that the set-up will be based on an evaluation in intervals, where measurements are carried out after a set-number of cycles.

Figure 5 shows the general physical set-up. The in-situ set-up at IKTS consists of two power supplies by Keithley (two SMUs (source measure units)), an oscilloscope, a needle card (on loan from KAI) and a custom-built adapter. Furthermore, the two SMUs and the oscilloscope are connected to a router that provides a small network for communication in between the hardware and the operator's laptop.

Figure 5: Top: General overview; bottom left: SMU 2636 (left), SMU 2461 (right down), oscilloscope (right up); bottom right: needle card (green), adapter box (black).

In general, the goal is to connect two different structures of the polyheater chip with the two different SMUs, connected via the needle card and a custom adapter.

The logical connection between the SMUs and the polyheater pads are shown in Figure 6, while the needle card layout (contacting the pads of the polyheater with fine needles and connects them to a Sub-D-Plug) is shown in Figure 7. Finally, the electrical layout of the adapter is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 6: Connections between the SMUs and the polyheater pads.

The temperature measurement lines of the polyheater pads (T_{force+} , T_{force-} , T_{sense+} and T_{sense-}) are connected to the Keithley 2636B SMU, allowing for direct measurements of the resistance and thereby temperature of the device. The heating pulse is produced by the Keithley SMU 2461, which is then further connected to the relevant polyheater pads (V_{poly+} , V_{poly-} , $Power+$ and $Power-$). The measurement line of the copper metallization itself could also be measured, however, this is not possible for all layouts and so was excluded from the general protocol.

Figure 7: Layout of the needle card female Sub-D connector in relation to the contacted polyheater pad.

As an adapter between the needle card and the power units, a dedicated adapter box was engineered by our IKTS internal electronics department. The connection diagram for this adapter box can be found in Figure 8. This adapter splits the Sub-D-connector into four banana plugs that are plugged into the SMU 2461 and over which the polysilicon can be heated and the pulses measured (in Four-Wire-Sense-Mode), as well as four BNC connectors that are plugged into the SMU 2636. These are used for measuring the temperature sensor, also in Four-Wire-Sense-Mode. Furthermore, two additional BNC cables leave the adapter box. On one, the inner and outer core are connected to the V_{poly+} and V_{poly-} pad respectively, and on the other BNC cable, the inner and outer core are connected to the T_{sense+} and T_{sense-} pad. This allows us to plug these two extra BNC cables into the oscilloscope and thereby plot their signal directly.

Figure 8: Connecting diagram for connection adapter box between the needle card and the SMUs.

A simple wireless router allows the operator’s laptop and electrical devices to be in the same sub-network, thereby enabling communication between them.

The chosen parameters for thermal cycling differ between samples due to different lengths of the polysilicon heating layer. In general, the parameters provided by KAI regarding bias and peak voltage were used as a guideline, but then optimized to reach the desired temperatures (resistances of the temperature sensor). Usually, the samples are designed to reach 100 °C of base and 400 °C of peak heating. The peaks are 200 μs long and are followed by a rest period, in which the sample cools down again. The rest period is timed in such a way, that the total time between the start of each pulse is one second.

These very specific parameters (short pulses at high voltages) can be well achieved by the Keithley SMU 2461. The other Keithley SMU 2636B was already present at the IKTS. The familiarity with the operation of Keithley SMUs as well as the capabilities of the new SMU 2636B are the reason why this specific hardware set-up was chosen.

2.2 Software solution

The communication between the operator’s laptop and the SMUs is executed via Visual Studio Code using the Lua scripting language and the Keithley TSP Toolkit Visual Studio Extension once they are all connected to the sub-network of the router. Both SMUs can be piloted individually by assigning them different nodes. In general, only the SMU 2461 is communicated with, since this is the one generating the pulses, while the other SMU just steadily measures the resistance of the temperature sensor. The operator sends the relevant script to the SMU, which then pulses independently until the stated amount of heating cycles are reached. The exact Lua script used in shown in Figure 9.

```

reset()
configListName = "myPulses"
                -- set levels for baseline bias voltage and max voltage level (stop)
                (pulse height is difference between bias_level and stop)
bias_level = 3.5 -- 4.7 for ph7001, 4.1 for ph5002, 3.5 ph300nv
stop = 35.2     -- 49 for ph7001, 47 for ph5002, 35.2 for ph300nv
pulse_width = 200e-6 -- 200 mu s pulse width
count = 2500    -- number of pulses
MeasureEnable = smu.ON
bufferName = defbuffer1
delay = 0
offTime = 999800e-6 -- difference from pulse width to 1 s
xBiasLimit = 1
xPulseLimit = 10.1
failAbort = smu.OFF
                -- Set the source to output current.
smu.source.func = smu.FUNC_DC_VOLTAGE
smu.source.readback = smu.OFF
                -- Set up the measure functions.
smu.digitize.func = smu.FUNC_DIGITIZE_CURRENT
smu.digitize.sense = smu.SENSE_4WIRE
smu.digitize.range = 20
smu.digitize.samplerate = 500000
defbuffer1.capacity = 1000000
                -- measure function of separate pulses trailing after each other
smu.source.pulsetrain(configListName, bias_level, stop, pulse_width, count, smu.ON,
bufferName, delay, offTime, xBiasLimit, xPulseLimit, failAbort)
trigger.model.initiate()
waitcomplete()

```

Figure 9: Lua script used to produce consecutive pulse trains, thereby cycling the polyheater sample.

2.3 Functionality Validation

It is essential to investigate the general electrical functionality of the set-up. For this purpose, the power pulse as well as the resistance of the temperature sensor were monitored with an oscilloscope.

Comparing the power pulses produced at KAI and the ones at IKTS, as show in Figure 10, it is immediately apparent that the pulse produced by the IKTS set-up is not rectangular, but rather “tooth”-shaped. Investigations showed that in our set-up, the pulse is generally only rectangular, if the voltages are relatively low (<10V). However, to reach the desired temperatures in the polyheater, it is necessary to use high voltages, resulting in those tooth shaped pulses. This leads to the heating ramp not being applied almost instantly to the material, as is the case at KAI, but rather as a sloped curve. Even though the peak voltages and the areas under the curves are almost identical for both set-ups, this discrepancy in peak shapes probably leads to a significantly reduced amount of thermo-mechanical stress in our set-up. This will be investigated later in the images taken of the cycled polyheater samples.

Figure 10: Comparison of pulse voltage against time between IKTS and KAI set-up.

Furthermore, we also investigated the signal from the temperature sensor and plotted it with the oscilloscope. Figure 11 shows an exemplary temperature curve from one of the cycling steps, the formula for temperature calculation was shown in the introduction and is based on the relationship between resistance and temperature of aluminium metal. The signal-to-noise-ratio is rather low so far, and efforts to improve the signal by testing different source amplitudes are underway. However, a general averaged trend can still be determined from the curve, although the area of uncertainty is fairly large, as indicated in the figure. Furthermore, one can identify that the sample reaches the desired base and peak temperature of 100 °C base and 400 °C peak.

Figure 11: Temperature sensor data during a single cycle. The raw, noisy data is shown in black, the average in red, and the array of uncertainty in green. Horizontal lines at roughly 100 °C and 400 °C indicate the base and peak level of the averaged temperature

Examining the evolution of the temperature sensor resistance also indicated an increase in resistance over the course of the cycling, which is also discussed in [4]. This results in a significant

change of the temperature reading, as shown in figure Figure 12. The data for the “before” graph was gathered right at the beginning of the cycling round, consisting of 2500 cycles, and the “after” data was gathered from the last cycle. Because the formula to calculate the temperature of the sensor also includes the room temperature resistance, the “before” curve uses the resistance value before this round of cycling, and the other one uses either the “before” or the “after” value of the room temperature resistance, with the latter value being gathered several minutes after the pulsing was finished.

The peak temperature seemingly decreases between the start and the end of the cycling. However, we judge it more probable that the temperature sensor itself significantly degrades during cycling, rather than that the Joule heating of the polysilicon, supplied with the same exact parameters for pulsing, becomes less efficient over time. This is an especially relevant consideration in this case, corroborated by the fact that in the IKTS set-up, the temperature sensor seems to degrade significantly more than in the previous study [4], increasing its resistance by up to 100% after 25000 cycles, instead of flattening out after an increase of 1%.

Figure 12: Comparison of temperature signal (averaged) before and after a cycling session (2500 cycles). Before this specific session, the sample already experienced 5000 pulses.

Finally, a comparison of the (averaged) temperature curve measured at IKTS with the one from KAI is shown in Figure 13. The same two temperature curves either start to increase at the same time or reach peak temperature at the same time. This difference was already indicated by the observation that the slope of the IKTS power pulse is significantly less steep, and it also takes a longer time to reach the peak temperature. Furthermore, the temperature drop-off is also less abrupt, therefore the sample remains at peak temperature longer. This corroborates the previously made assumption, that the tooth-shaped heating pulse is not equal in effect to the rectangular one. These differences in heat application are further investigated with the imaging results in later chapters.

Figure 13: Comparison of temperature pulse curve measured with the KAI or the IKTS set-up. Left: Temperature increase starts at the same time for both curves. Right: The IKTS curve is artificially time-shifted, so that both temperature peaks occur at the same time

Chapter 3 Sample design

3.1 Challenge

The major challenge for designing an in-situ polyheater chip is to keep the chip functionality while providing an 180° access corridor for the x-ray beam characterization. In addition to the chip design, the heat actuation needs to be adjusted by replacing the used needle card by a small custom-designed PCB. This is required to fit the entire system on the instrumental stage, to avoid chip handling/mounting steps in between successive nano-XCT scans. After extensive ex-situ study following in-situ chip requirements were identified: Sample rotation axis needs to be parallel to the long chip edge, the Si substrate thickness must be below 60 μm , a freestanding line like Cu features of interest (width below 40 μm) with a line orientation parallel to the rotation axis. These requirements can be fulfilled using two different approaches, described within the sections 3.2 and 3.3.

3.2 In-situ polyheater chips via back preparation

Based on the testing requirements of previous projects and studies, numerous polyheater chip designs have been developed and manufactured on a wafer-level process. By chance, some of them are even “partly” fulfilling the major requirements of nanoXCT characterization. To provide first structures, KAI has back-prepared available polyheater chips, to enable preliminary nanoXCT measurements and start the screening for the optimum sample parameters. The Si substrate has a thickness of 120 μm . To provide chips with a uniform thickness of 60 μm , several chips with a suitable line design were thinned via industrial plasma etching patch process. Subsequently the chips were glued and bonded on a customized PCB, suitable to fit on the nanoXCT sample stage (Figure 14 a-b). To keep the dimensions as small as possible, only six contacting wires/pads were used (2x power cycling, 4x temperature sensing). Finally, the sample power pads (chip side) were partly removed, and the sensing pads (chip top) were entirely removed using laser cutting. To keep the chip functional, the polycrystalline heating structure as well as the elongated power contacting via (below the chip surface) were entirely preserved. Functional tests confirmed that the central Cu line structure can be still thermo-mechanical cycled (including 4-point resistance measurement for temperature control).

Figure 14: a) Customized PCB to enable chip actuation without using a needle card. b) Back prepared polyheater chip, glued and bonded on dedicated PCB. c) New polyheater design (X-MAS tree) with protruding Cu structures marked in green.

3.3 Redesign and manufacturing of dedicated in-situ polyheater chips

To avoid the tedious back preparation of polyheater chips in future, new designs and processing routines were developed at KAI/Infineon. Figure 14c shows one of the newly designed polyheater structures, where the green marked areas are copper structures protruding up to 20 μm out of the chip surface. While the thick copper structures on the sensing (and power) pads are needed for wire bonding, the central structure represents the region of interest. Due to this dedicated design, the provided structure for thermomechanical stress testing can be imaged within a 180° X-ray access corridor, even without back preparation.

The new wafer processing routine includes a wafer level thin process (down to 60 μm) as well as a two-step copper deposition. Here, a thin base layer is deposited first (< 2 μm), followed by a thick power metallization in the green marked areas. Figure 14c shows the so-called X-Mas tree layout as one example for dedicated nanoXCT designs. This structure provides a copper feature with six sections (differing in line/pad width) to enable multiple lab X-ray characterization methodologies as well as stress states on one single sample. While the blue sections S1 (13 μm), S2 (25 μm) and S3 (35 μm) are suitable for nanoXCT, the yellow sections S4 (80 μm), S5 (160 μm) and S6 (280 μm) enable “quick” 2D radiographic projection scans, as well as μCT imaging.

Chapter 4 In-situ imaging

4.1 2D imaging

The cycled IKTS in-situ sample shown here has a layout called PH5002 #5, with a copper thickness of 5 μm , a silicon backing of 120 μm and a “U”-shaped copper structure as shown in the light microscope image in Chapter 1.2.1, with a copper line width of 40 μm . The thick silicon backing attenuates the transmitted beam significantly, therefore the images gathered so far are noisy, even though they were taken with a long illumination time of three minutes per image.

Figure 15 a)-d) shows the evolution of the crack formation over the thermal cycling of one of the U-shaped copper lines with a line width of 40 μm . Each image was taken in the same area very close to the center of the structure at intervals of 2500 pulses, with the total number of pulses noted in the top left corner of each image. Figure 15 e)-h) shows the same images, but due to the high level of noise, some chosen cracks were marked with colored lines, to increase visibility. Each time a new crack network appears clearly at a given step, it is marked with a new color and then further shown in this color in the following steps. The strong variety in grey values and seemingly indefinable bright and dark spots are characteristics of the X-ray microscope and cannot be avoided.

Figure 15: a)-d) Evolution of crack formation in a sample cycled in four rounds, each round amassing 2500 pulses. e)-h) The same images of a cycled sample as above, but significant cracks are marked in a new color once they first appear, retaining that color through the later images.

Comparing the two last images of Figure 15, it seems like there is barely any new crack development between 7500 and 10000 cycles. This is further examined in Figure 16, which shows the same sample cycled at IKTS, first cycled 10000 times, then an additional 15000 times adding up to 25000, in comparison to a similar, comparable sample cycled directly to 25000 cycles at KAI, though the latter one was cycled with peak pulse temperatures of 450°C, instead of 400°C. An additional sample will be cycled at IKTS in the upcoming weeks with the higher peak pulse temperature, to provide adequate comparison material.

Figure 16: 2D mosaics of a sample cycled at IKTS to 10k cycles (top), the same sample cycled further to 25k cycled (middle), and a comparable sample cycled at KAI to 25k cycles.

There seems to be barely any development between 10000 and 25000 cycles in the IKTS sample, though potentially a 3D view could provide more information on that. Furthermore, the exact crack network is hard to identify due to the high noise of the images. Periodic bright spots in the image are once again just an effect of the X-ray microscope and the image stitching.

The KAI sample shows more pronounced cracks and voids, some parts of copper seem to have migrated far enough from their original position for the line to appear strongly deformed in its shape, with chunks missing. This extreme degradation is not visible in the IKTS sample, which retains its geometry even after 25000 heating pulses. This might be because the KAI sample was heated to slightly higher peak pulse temperatures (450°C instead of 400°C).

This means that although the sample could be cycled and imaged in sequence multiple times, with a visible crack network evolution, the degradation is significantly less pronounced than in comparable samples cycled at KAI.

4.2 3D imaging

As describe in Chapter 3, new sample layouts were designed specifically to enable non-destructive, in-situ 3D imaging. However, due to delays in production, they were not ready in time to be cycled and imaged at IKTS. This will be a focus of the work at IKTS in the upcoming weeks and months.

Chapter 5 Summary and Conclusion

The in-situ set-up at IKTS was successfully commissioned, and its electrical layout and components described in detail. The generated power and heating pulses were intensely investigated, showing significant differences to the ones generated in the KAI set-up.

Specialized 3D samples were engineered and produced in at Infineon Technologies Austria and KAI, and wire bonded to customized PCB boards and plugs. Their copper structure is elevated, compared to the surrounding area, and irrelevant parts are cut away and thinned, while still retaining the functionality of the polyheater; thereby enabling in-situ 3D imaging.

Several 2D samples were successfully cycled and imaged in mosaic format, one same being shown here as an example. Although the images were not of the desired quality in signal-to-noise-ratio, they still showed the growth of several cracks over the cycling steps, thereby providing a solid proof of concept that the in-situ set-up at IKTS is functional.

But although polyheater samples could be cycled and then imaged in sequence multiple times, with a visible crack network evolution, the degradation is seemingly less strong than in similar samples cycled at KAI, even though heat load and heating rates are comparable. Together with the observed differences in the shape of the power pulse and the slope of the temperature curve, added evaluation of the differences between the IKTS and KAI set-up with previous studies [2] will be essential in the further course of this project. It will have to be determined whether the degradation mechanisms are still mostly based on distinct cracking, or whether surface roughing plays a more significant role. Furthermore, it is to be discussed in the future with the relevant experts at KAI and from the modelling group, whether an increase in cycling temperature would be a viable solution for this issue.

Chapter 6 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
TXM	Transmission X-ray microscopy
ROI	Region of interest
Cu	copper
nanoXCT	Nanoscale X-ray computed tomography
μ CT	Microscale X-ray computed tomography
IKTS	Fraunhofer Institute for ceramic technologies and systems
ARMI	Advanced X-ray microscope (with dual energy source: Ga and In)
SMU	Source Measure Unit

Chapter 7 Literature

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